

PEDAGOGICAL RELEVANCE OF THE BHAGAVAD GITA IN CONTEMPORARY TEACHER EDUCATION UNDER NEP 2020

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Abstract

The Bhagavad Gita, is universally renowned as the precious jewel/ Kohinoor of ancient India's spiritual wisdom that is timeless, classless and formless. It is revered as on zenith of all philosophical texts, that provides insights into human cognition, social reconstruction, ethics of duty, karmic philosophy, human values etc. It serves as a vital catalyst for developing well balanced, emotionally intelligent, spiritually aligned, ethically just and highly spirited teacher educators. With the official announcement and approval of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, by the Union Cabinet of India on July 29, 2020. The policy provides different timelines for its various recommendations, with the overall goal of a complete transformation of the education system at all levels by around year 2040 in India. It emphasizes holistic, value-based, multidisciplinary education that is based on ancient Indian knowledge system, revisiting the timeless principles of the Bhagavad Gita becomes particularly relevant in

The present paper delves into the relevance of the Bhagavad Gita's philosophy into teacher education programs, enhancing the spiritual, moral and physio-emotional dimensions of future teachers. The Bhagavad Gita offers a evolutionary framework for human growth and development that aligns remarkably well with the three domains of learning identified in modern educational psychology- Cognitive, Affective, and Psychomotor. Its teachings not only promote intellectual clarity but also nurture emotional maturity and disciplined Karma or action, making it deeply relevant to teacher education. It further proposes pedagogical applications based on experiential learning methodology rooted in Gita's teachings and their alignment with modern educational practices based on "Nishkam Karma" or "Action without desire for reward." That emerge from its core ethical teachings on altruistic deeds standing on the strong pillars of righteousness (dharma), selflessness, and spiritual wisdom. It can be meaningfully adapted and applied at all stages of education as per school education structure (5+3+3+4 Model) of NEP 2020. This structure comprised four stages: the Foundational stage for children aged 3 to 8 years, the Preparatory stage for those aged 8 to 11 years, the Middle stage for learners aged 11 to 14 years, and the Secondary stage for adolescents aged 14 to 18 years.

1. Introduction

The holy book Bhagavad Gita has been regarded as one of the significant spiritual books for centuries and impacted number of people throughout the human history. The book Gita is an Indian classic epic Mahabharata which tells the story of two families descended from two brothers who inherit a kingdom from their father. Within this larger narrative story appears The Bhagavad Gita, a conversational poem between Lord Krishna and Arjuna. This conversation serves as manual for self-realization, leadership, and moral conduct, qualities essential for teachers. Bhagavad Gita consists 700 Sanskrit verses which is divided into 18 chapters. Gita can be found in chapters 25 to 42 of the book of Bheeshma in the classic Hindu epic The Mahabharata. Most of the verses appear in the *anushtap* meter, where each verse has a total of 32 letters with 8 words in each of the four quadrants. Some verses in the 15th chapter appear in *trishtup* meter with 44 words. As per Sri Raghavendra Teertha, the 18 chapters can be broadly classified into 3 sections with 6 chapters in each section. Bhagavad Gita is divided into three sections: chapters 1-6 (Karma Yoga) focus on selfless action, duty and teaching detachment; chapters 7-12 (Bhakti Yoga) emphasize on devotion and divine; chapters 13-18 (Jnana Yoga) cover the liberation, understanding the self and spiritual knowledge. Additionally, the Gita is thought to express at least ten distinct meanings, that all are consistent with one another. Chapter 2 of the Gita will provide an example of various meaning. There are three important interpretations of the --historical, psychological and spiritual. It is also based on individual, physical, biological, mental, social, cultural, aesthetical, professional, logical, rational, behavioural, moral, devotional, metaphysical, astronomical, universal meanings. These are applicable beyond time, space & Circumstances or Context. These three together are used to explain how meaning, action, or interpretation can change depending on *when*, *where*, and *under what conditions* something happens.

The Mahabharata, dates back to 5000 B.C., is still read and followed by majority of Hindu's worldwide. Even today it is of cognitive significance, affective resonance and psychomotor strength. It is a tale reflecting the absolute human values man beyond time and space. It is suitable for young and elderly simultaneously and provides righteousness among four stages of life called *āśramas*. The first stage is Brahmacharya or studentship that focuses on reading, learning, discipline, and morality. The second stage is Gr̥hastha, it starts after marriage and supports familial social structure. The third stage is Vānaprastha, when elders, translates responsibilities and power to the next generation, and leads a spiritual, peaceful and isolated life. The final stage is Sannyāsa, when in old age people sacrifices all materialistic things, seeks

inner peace and lives a peaceful life with meditation, studies Vedas, Ramayan, Bhagvad Gita, and other sacred texts. It develops an extreme sense self-realization and unity with the absolute power or divine. It just aims to attain Nirvana or liberation from universal cycle of births and rebirths ultimately.

2. Guru-Shishya Parampara: sacred golden era beyond time, location and space

Guru Drona, is strong anchor of the story, he had many disciples including prince Kauravas and Pandavas and his own son. His individualised teaching, warfare strategical training, skill and competency-based teaching with focus on pragmatistic philosophy were the ultimate benchmarks that made him the most renowned and learned teacher. He advocated Bhartiya Gyan Parampara, experiential learning, problem-based learning, project-based learning, collaborative learning, action and applied research methodologies were way ahead of his counterparts. If it is regarded as something beyond and a real tale, it demonstrates the presence of evolved human beings. All the characters in the epic were highly learned and were disciples of guru Drona (Boray, 2023). The Guru–Shishya Parampara, revived in NEP 2020, highlights Krishna and Arjuna bond—as a relationship based on support, strategic counsel, and unwavering commitment to righteous conduct.” In the Gita, Krishna does not impose knowledge; he facilitates reflection, strengthens Arjuna’s inner resolve, and guides him towards self-realization. This becomes a powerful model for contemporary teacher training: teachers must learn to act as facilitators and mentors who encourage critical thinking, decision making, psychological endurance, and individualised learning rather than merely transmitting information. IKS encourages teachers to connect classroom learning with India’s vast traditions in astronomy, medicine, mathematics, logic, ecology, arts, languages, surgery and wellness sciences such as Yoga, naturopathy and ayurveda. The Gita reinforces this holistic approach through its multidimensional understanding of knowledge—*jnana* (conceptual understanding), *vijnana* (applied knowledge), and *atma-jnana* (self-knowledge).

We learn from Bhagavad Gita that questioning is a tool for learning. Arjuna asks so many questions from Lord Krishna and satisfied his doubts. It shows that students may learn better if they ask questions from their teachers and teachers also allow to them for the same. Sometimes students become impatient. To deal with such situations it is important on the part of the teacher to clarify the doubts of the students. Arjuna respected Lord Krishna as his mentor and Krishna also respect the queries raised by the Arjuna. Such type of relationship enhances the classroom environment positively. Krishna uses different methods to clear the doubts of

Arjuna like, stories, examples, reasoning etc. which makes our learning deeper. Bhagavad Gita shows that effective pedagogy involves addressing both intellectual and emotional needs. “Arjuna, the favourite disciple of Guru Drona, was highly skilled, trained and educated; his mind was just clouded by a fleeting delusion. Seizing that moment, Krishna chose it as the perfect occasion to reveal the divine wisdom of the *Bhagavad Gita*. We all are prone to self-doubts and weaknesses. Hence, ‘Bhagavad Gita’ is a lesson to overcome our own life struggles and hurdles at home, or in society at large. Arjuna was imparted profound wisdom in the midst of the chaos of the battle of righteousness by Lord Krishna. It was a moment in life when anyone may feel weak and completely blank. This incident teaches us the importance of life lessons which helps individuals to learn how to remain calm and be strong during such challenging situations in life. Therefore, Bhagavad Gita should be included in the curriculum at the elementary, secondary and higher education levels.

The Gita emphasizes the cultivation of inner virtues such as cognition, self-discipline, righteousness, detachment from outcomes (Nishkama Karma), equanimity in mind, thought, words and karma. This aligns closely with NEP 2020’s call for inculcating essential human values and life skills i.e., advance level of empathy, integrity, responsibility, respect for diversity, and environmental consciousness—in learners. For teacher training, this perspective insists that teachers must first internalize these values to become friend, philosopher & guide. As the Gita holds significant relevance for contemporary teacher education, as it highlights the centrality of teacher educators’ personality, character, behaviour, and ethical disposition in shaping learners’ behaviour, values and mindset. NEP 2020 envisions an educational ecosystem that is ethical, holistic, and deeply grounded in Indian cultural heritage and civilization. Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS) exhibit a deep conformity with the pedagogical and philosophical tenets of the Bhagavad Gita, a foundational sacred text that continues to mould the educational thought within the broader Indian intelligentsia. This provides a powerful pedagogical framework for teacher education institutions seeking to design presently feasible yet socio-culturally rooted and value-based training and skill-based program. Bhagavad Gita and the objectives of NEP 2020 synchronize to provide a pedagogical module for teachers’ behaviour modification and skill development in present time. It focuses on overall grooming and personality development of educators who are not only pedagogically skilled but also ethically stable, spiritually balanced and scientifically updated. Such teachers can truly shape the enlightened learners sitting in classroom benches, playing in playgrounds, experimenting in

laboratories and acquiring skills for holistic learning towards the realization of mission Viksit Bharat 2047.

The *Bhagavad Gita* provides strong meta-philosophical base that can be meaningfully applied to contemporary teacher education beyond time, location and space. Its pedagogical relevance emerges through its holistic vision of wisdom, good moral conduct, emotional stability, and ethical accountability —dimensions that align closely with modern educational expectations. The text positions the teacher as both a friend, philosopher moral guide and a reflective mentor, a view that resonates with current discourses in educational philosophy, psychology and professional standards and ethics. The two-way communication method used by Krishna to guide Arjuna illustrates the importance of learner-centred, individualised instruction and action research. His teaching adapts continuously to Arjuna's cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains, principles of level- specific teaching, differential instructional strategy and problem-solving approach advocated in contemporary pedagogical theory. Gita's relevance for teacher education programmes aims to foster holistic education with inclusive classrooms and adaptive instructional methodologies.

Finally, the Gita emphasises continuous self-improvisation and channelisation of one's energies on the path of righteousness and universal truth, which may be equated with global standards of quality education for all. By integrating these principles into teacher education curricula, institutions can enrich value-based education and promote a holistic understanding of the teacher's role that inculcates strong value system based on Karmic philosophy, strong character formation and social betterment of human race.

3. Unified summary of chapter-wise analysis of the *Bhagavad Gita*

The *Bhagavad Gita*, presents a comprehensive blueprint for human evolution and civilization spanning knowledge, focused action, human values, and spirituality. Beginning with Arjuna's moral dilemma in Chapter 1, the text progressively guides the learner toward clarity, balance, and purposeful action. It can be correlated with the confusion and dilemma an individual or student faces in day-to-day life between which path to follow among absolutely right or practically best.

Chapters 2–6 establish foundational wisdom, including the nature of the self, the importance of equanimity, selfless action, ethical intention, and mental discipline through meditation, karma Yoga etc. It supports students or individuals to manage examination phobia, outcome related anxiety, performance insecurity, and academic pressure. By encouraging focus on effort

to study or do tasks, not on marks or results only. It builds emotional intelligence, resilience, decision-making and rational thinking.

Chapters 7–12 deepen philosophical and devotional understanding, encouraging holistic perception, faith, compassion, and an expanded worldview symbolised in the cosmic vision. It emphasizes the exploration of absolute knowledge over just jumbled information, crystal clear vision, concentration, discipline and highly thoughtful goals. It appreciates basic values such as sincerity, humility, gratitude, and faith in oneself.

Chapters 13–15 explore consciousness, the distinction between present body and absolute soul, it demarcates the transient physical body and the timeless self, reminding students/ individuals that their existence is not defined by examination grades, marks, or inconsistent sentiments. It also elaborates the three *gunas*—*sattoguna*, *rajoguna*, and *tamoguna* that makes one's habits, attitude, choices, interests, and overall behaviour, It utilises the symbolic inverted cosmic tree for detachment from negative values or variables and to inspire individuals to stay grounded with strong value system and ultimate purpose.

Chapters 16–17 highlight virtues, values, and the influence of the three *gunas* on one's character and belief system, thereby strengthening overall moral development.

The text culminates in Chapter 18, which synthesises all paths towards absolute truth beauty and goodness—into a holistic approach to human liberation and righteousness. Collectively, the Gita nurtures cognitive clarity, emotional stability, ethical conduct, and disciplined action, aligning closely with modern educational aims, especially those emphasising holistic development, experiential learning, value-based learning, and strong character development.

The pedagogical theoretical base embedded in various chapters of the *Bhagavad Gita* complements reflective level of teaching practice, learner centered teaching and counselling approaches, logical reasoning, ethical prudence and holistic development. These insights support the correlation of Bhagvad Gita's philosophical foundations into latest teacher education curricula, based on NEP 2020 that strongly advocates Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS), human values-based learning, pedagogical empowerment and Continuous professional development (CPD) advancement.

Krishna's bidirectional communication with Arjuna in the *Bhagavad Gita* highlights learner-centred pedagogical and individualised counselling approach. Throughout the text, Krishna adjusts the complexity, organization, personalised instruction and medium of communication based on Arjuna's socio- emotional status, cognitive readiness, and spatial cognition. Rather than presenting a fixed theoretical framework, he engages Arjun in one-to-one dialogue, with

reflective level of questioning, involving higher order thinking, emotional equanimity and collaborative learning meaning-making—processes that closely align with principles of social constructivism. This approach emphasises that knowledge is co-constructed through interaction, open dialogue, and constructive debate between teacher and learner. Krishna’s use of metaphors, scaffolded explanations, and empathetic responses mirrors contemporary constructivist and social constructivist pedagogies, which stress personalised learning, learner agency, and relevance of interpersonal communication in knowledge transaction. By tailoring his teaching to Arjuna’s evolving needs and co-creating understanding through sustained dialogue, Krishna models an adaptive, differentiated, and socially mediated instructional process consistent with modern theories of meaningful learning.

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 highlights the revitalization of Bhartiya Gyana Parampara (IKS), the significance of value-based education, and the development of holistic development. The Bhagavad Gita aligns profoundly with this vision, offering metaphysical and pedagogical doctrine that inform contemporary education. A central idea emphasized in NEP 2020 is the integration of spatial cognition and *viveka* or critical thinking to foster analytical thinking, problem-solving, and independent judgment. This resonates with lord Krishna’s enlightened educational philosophy.

“तस्मादज्ञानसम्भूतं हृत्स्थं ज्ञानासिनात्मनः।

छित्त्वेन संशयं योगमातिष्ठोत्तिष्ठ भारत॥” (भगवद्गीता 4.42)

“Therefore, sever the doubts arising from ignorance residing in your heart with the sword of knowledge, and stand firm in the path of yoga, O Arjuna.”

This verse aligns with NEP’s aim of nurturing inquiry-driven, critically reflective learners capable of navigating complex knowledge environments. Similarly, the Gita’s focus on *samskāra* (ethical and moral formation) supports NEP 2020’s emphasis on values, empathy, integrity, and responsible citizenship. The scripture advocates a holistic view of human development, nurturing balance across physical, emotional, intellectual, and spiritual domains—an approach directly mirrored in NEP’s call for integrated and experiential learning, mental well-being, yoga, arts, and sports. By weaving the Gita’s timeless pedagogical wisdom into teacher education, curricular design, and classroom culture, NEP 2020 promotes an educational ecosystem that is culturally rooted, ethically grounded, and oriented toward cultivating self-aware, resilient, and compassionate individuals prepared for the challenges of the 21st century.

4. Conclusion

The philosophical foundations of the *Bhagavad Gita* align closely with the knowledge translation and learning outcomes-based objectives articulated in the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. The Gita's emphasis on self-knowledge (*jnana*), emotional regulation, ethical righteousness (*dharma*), and selfless action (*nishkama karma*) resonates with the policy's vision of developing intellectually agile, emotionally resilient, and morally responsible learners. Integrating these principles within the 5+3+3+4 structure of NEP 2020 reinforces its commitment to holistic development, experiential and competency-based learning

The cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains of learning converge within the ethical and contemplative framework of the Gita provides teacher education with a deeper pedagogical knowledge, human values and right competencies and skill sets. The synchronisation of Bhagwad Gita-inspired skill-based learning with NEP 2020's educational aspirations strengthen the cultivation of learned, ethical, empathetic, and competent educators, thereby eventually catalysing towards India becoming *Viswa guru* and the attainment of national vision of *Viksit Bharat* by 2047.

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